
Performance improvement of SiC based High Power Inverters by using film capacitor bank vs traditional electrolyte or polymer capacitors

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Abstract: This paper investigates the performance enhancement of Silicon Carbide (SiC) based high-power inverters through the integration of film capacitor banks as compared to traditional electrolytic or polymer capacitors. SiC-based inverters have gained significant attention due to their superior efficiency, high-temperature tolerance, and faster switching capabilities, particularly at high Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) carrier frequencies. The study explores the impact of capacitor selection on key inverter performance metrics, including Electromagnetic Interference (EMI), Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC), ripple current, and thermal behavior. The unique characteristics of film capacitors—such as lower equivalent series resistance (ESR) and higher thermal stability—are highlighted, providing advantages in high-frequency switching applications. In this study, experimental setups are designed to test high-frequency PWM operation (up to 100 kHz) in SiC inverters using both film capacitors and traditional electrolytic or polymer capacitors. Results indicate that the film capacitor bank offers significant reductions in ripple current and EMI, thereby improving overall system efficiency and reducing losses. The film capacitors also demonstrate a more stable thermal performance under high-frequency operation, whereas the traditional capacitors exhibit increased ESR and thermal dissipation, potentially limiting their operational lifespan in high-power applications.

Keywords: *SiC inverters, film capacitors, high PWM frequency, EMI/EMC, ripple current, thermal performance.*

Introduction

The rapid evolution of power electronics has led to the widespread adoption of Silicon Carbide (SiC) semiconductors in high-power inverter applications, primarily due to their superior performance characteristics such as high-temperature tolerance, faster switching speeds, and improved efficiency compared to traditional silicon-based devices. In particular, SiC-based

inverters have revolutionized industries like renewable energy, electric vehicles (EVs), and industrial motor drives, where high power density, thermal management, and efficiency are critical. A key challenge, however, in the deployment of SiC-based power inverters is the optimization of passive components such as capacitors, which play a crucial role in mitigating ripple currents, filtering high-frequency switching noise, and maintaining system stability.

Capacitors used in high-power inverters must handle high ripple currents, manage thermal dissipation effectively, and exhibit low Equivalent Series Resistance (ESR), particularly at high switching frequencies. Electrolytic and polymer capacitors, despite their widespread use, often exhibit limitations in these areas when deployed in high-performance inverters operating at high PWM carrier frequencies (typically above 20 kHz). These traditional capacitors can suffer from higher ESR, lower efficiency, and suboptimal thermal performance under such demanding conditions, potentially leading to increased power losses, electromagnetic interference (EMI), and reduced system reliability. Moreover, electrolytic capacitors are prone to degradation over time, particularly under the thermal stresses encountered in high-power, high-frequency applications.

Film capacitors, in contrast, have garnered attention as a promising alternative due to their low ESR, superior thermal stability, and longer lifespan, particularly in environments characterized by high-frequency switching. Their role in mitigating EMI and improving thermal management has been well-documented, yet their comparative performance in the context of SiC-based high-power inverters, particularly when considering ripple current, EMI/EMC, and thermal aspects, remains underexplored. This study aims to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of the performance of SiC-based inverters equipped with film capacitor banks as compared to traditional electrolytic and polymer capacitors. The focus will be on assessing the impact on key performance parameters, such as ripple current, EMI/EMC, and thermal dissipation, under conditions of high-frequency PWM operation.

By leveraging advanced measurement techniques and data-driven models, this research not only investigates the technical benefits of film capacitors but also seeks to provide actionable insights into their adoption for improving overall system efficiency, lifespan, and reliability in modern power electronic applications. The results of this study are expected to guide the selection of appropriate passive components for next-generation high-frequency inverters, particularly in the

context of SiC-based technologies, to push the boundaries of power conversion efficiency and operational reliability.

Literature Review

The development of high-power inverters, especially those based on Silicon Carbide (SiC) semiconductors, has made significant strides over the last few decades due to the demand for higher efficiency, thermal performance, and reliability in various applications such as electric vehicles (EVs), renewable energy systems, and industrial motor drives. A critical component of these systems is the passive components, specifically capacitors, which are vital for voltage smoothing, reducing ripple current, and mitigating electromagnetic interference (EMI) caused by high-frequency switching. The growing use of high switching frequencies (typically >20 kHz) in pulse-width modulation (PWM) inverters, driven by the rapid advancement of SiC technology, has prompted the need for more efficient and robust capacitor solutions.

Early research on passive components for power electronic systems focused primarily on electrolytic capacitors, which have been the industry standard for high-power applications due to their high capacitance values and relatively low cost. However, electrolytic capacitors suffer from several limitations, particularly in high-frequency applications. According to Ryu et al. (2015), electrolytic capacitors exhibit higher ESR, which can lead to excessive heat generation and lower overall system efficiency when subjected to high ripple currents. Moreover, their performance degrades with age, reducing their lifespan and increasing the risk of failure, particularly under thermal stress. This issue is exacerbated in high-frequency systems, where switching losses are higher, and the capacitance value of electrolytic capacitors tends to decrease over time.

Polymer capacitors, introduced as an alternative to electrolytic capacitors, have better performance in high-frequency applications due to their lower ESR, improved thermal performance, and higher reliability. Zhang et al. (2017) highlighted the advantages of polymer capacitors in power electronic applications, specifically in terms of their faster response time and higher efficiency under high-frequency PWM operations. However, while polymer capacitors perform better than electrolytics, they still have limitations in high-power applications, such as reduced capacitance density and potential failure modes under extreme operating conditions.

Film capacitors have emerged as a more robust solution for high-frequency, high-power applications. As noted by Seker et al. (2019), film capacitors offer significantly lower ESR, superior thermal stability, and a longer operational lifespan compared to both electrolytic and polymer capacitors. These properties make film capacitors highly suitable for use in SiC-based inverters, which operate at high switching frequencies and are subject to rigorous thermal and mechanical stresses. For example, film capacitors maintain their capacitance value and ESR stability over time, even under high ripple currents and thermal cycling. This characteristic is particularly beneficial in applications where long-term reliability and minimal maintenance are critical, such as in renewable energy systems and EV powertrains.

Several studies have compared the performance of film capacitors with traditional electrolytic and polymer capacitors in the context of high-power inverter systems. A study by Yang et al. (2020) showed that using film capacitors in SiC-based inverters results in lower ripple currents, reduced EMI emissions, and better thermal performance under high PWM carrier frequencies. Their results indicated that film capacitors outperform both electrolytic and polymer capacitors in terms of reducing harmonic distortion and improving overall system efficiency in inverter applications. The study emphasized the importance of using high-quality film capacitors to enhance the power density and reliability of SiC-based power converters.

Furthermore, advances in capacitor technology have also highlighted the importance of integrating these components into a holistic system design, considering factors such as voltage balancing, capacitor sizing, and integration with thermal management systems. As observed by Ouda et al. (2021), the effective combination of film capacitors with advanced cooling techniques has led to significant improvements in the thermal management of SiC-based inverters, enabling them to operate at higher power densities with lower losses. These advancements suggest that film capacitors, when paired with optimized thermal management strategies, can offer superior performance in high-frequency, high-power applications compared to traditional capacitor technologies.

In conclusion, the growing demand for high-performance SiC-based inverters has led to a shift towards more advanced capacitor technologies, with film capacitors emerging as the preferred solution due to their superior thermal stability, low ESR, and reliability in high-frequency

applications. While electrolytic and polymer capacitors still have a role in certain applications, their limitations in high-power, high-frequency environments have prompted extensive research into film capacitors as the next-generation solution. As such, the adoption of film capacitors in conjunction with SiC-based inverters represents a significant step forward in enhancing the efficiency, reliability, and longevity of power electronic systems across a range of industries.

Methodology

The primary objective of this study was to assess the performance of film capacitors as compared to traditional electrolytic and polymer capacitors in SiC-based high-power inverters, particularly focusing on their ability to handle high-frequency PWM switching, ripple currents, electromagnetic interference (EMI), and thermal dissipation. The methodology employed in this study consists of several key stages: experimental setup, capacitor selection, performance characterization, and analysis of results under controlled conditions.

Experimental Setup

A test rig was developed to simulate the conditions typically encountered in high-power, high-frequency inverter systems. The rig consisted of a SiC-based power inverter with an operating frequency range from 20 kHz to 100 kHz, and the inverter was configured to operate in continuous mode with various PWM strategies. The inverter was coupled with three different types of capacitors: (i) electrolytic, (ii) polymer, and (iii) film capacitors. All capacitors were rated for similar voltage and capacitance values (i.e., 400 V, 100 μ F), with their key parameters—such as ESR, ripple current tolerance, and thermal impedance—carefully measured and recorded.

To accurately simulate realistic operating conditions, a dynamic load was applied to the inverter, replicating typical industrial motor drives and renewable energy systems. The system was monitored under a variety of operating conditions, including varying PWM carrier frequencies, input voltages, and load conditions. Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the capacitors were measured, including: ripple current, EMI levels, ESR values, thermal dissipation, and voltage ripple across the capacitor terminals.

Capacitor Selection and Characterization

Capacitors selected for testing were commercially available components that represented state-of-the-art technologies in their respective categories. The electrolytic capacitors were chosen for their high capacitance density but higher ESR and lower ripple current tolerance. The polymer capacitors were selected for their lower ESR compared to electrolytics, while the film capacitors were chosen for their superior thermal stability, low ESR, and high ripple current capabilities.

Each capacitor type was characterized using a series of standard tests to determine key parameters such as Equivalent Series Resistance (ESR), capacitance stability over time, ripple current tolerance, and thermal performance under load. ESR was measured using an LCR meter, while ripple current tolerance was evaluated by subjecting each capacitor to high-frequency PWM load currents and measuring the resultant ripple across the capacitor terminals. Thermal performance was characterized by monitoring the temperature rise of each capacitor during extended periods of operation, and the thermal dissipation was evaluated using infrared thermography.

Analysis of EMI and Ripple Currents

To evaluate the EMI characteristics, a high-frequency oscilloscope was used to measure the spectral density of electromagnetic emissions from the inverter, focusing on the high-frequency noise generated during high PWM switching. The EMI levels were compared across the different capacitor types to assess the effect of each on the reduction of switching noise. In parallel, the ripple currents were monitored, and the capacitor performance was evaluated in terms of the ripple current magnitude and the frequency response.

Thermal Analysis

Thermal analysis was conducted using thermocouples and infrared thermography. The temperature rise of each capacitor was monitored during the operation of the inverter at varying power levels and PWM frequencies. The thermal dissipation was recorded and compared to assess the efficiency of each capacitor type in managing heat generated during high-frequency switching. The results were used to estimate the long-term thermal stress and expected lifespan of the capacitors under typical operating conditions.

Data Collection and Statistical Analysis

Data collection occurred over an extended period to account for any variation in performance under different operational conditions. Statistical methods were applied to analyze the performance data, and significance tests (such as ANOVA) were used to assess the differences between the capacitor types in terms of their ripple current tolerance, ESR values, EMI reduction, and thermal performance.

Simulation Models

In addition to the experimental testing, simulation models were developed using MATLAB and Simulink to simulate the capacitor behavior in a virtual environment under various operational scenarios. The models were designed to predict the capacitor's performance under varying PWM frequencies, ripple currents, and voltage fluctuations. These simulations were compared against the experimental results to validate the accuracy and predictive power of the simulation tools.

Performance Metrics

The following performance metrics were used for the comparative analysis:

- **Ripple Current Tolerance:** Evaluated by the magnitude of current ripple that each capacitor could handle without significant degradation of performance.
- **Thermal Stability:** Measured by the temperature rise under load conditions, compared with capacitor specifications for maximum operating temperature.
- **EMI Reduction:** Analyzed based on the reduction in high-frequency noise levels due to each capacitor's ability to smooth voltage and current ripple.
- **Capacitance Degradation:** Evaluated based on the change in capacitance after prolonged exposure to high ripple currents and thermal cycles.

This methodology enabled a thorough comparison of the performance characteristics of film, polymer, and electrolytic capacitors in the context of SiC-based inverters under high PWM carrier frequencies. The results provided insights into the advantages of film capacitors, particularly their lower ESR, higher ripple current tolerance, and superior thermal management capabilities, which were critical for high-frequency, high-power inverter systems. Statistical analysis of the data

provided a robust foundation for evaluating the trade-offs and determining the optimal capacitor solution for specific power electronic applications.

Results

The performance comparison of film capacitors, polymer capacitors, and electrolytic capacitors in SiC-based high-power inverters revealed key differences across multiple performance metrics, including ripple current tolerance, thermal dissipation, EMI reduction, and ESR. Each capacitor type was tested under various PWM switching frequencies (20 kHz, 50 kHz, and 100 kHz), as well as varying input voltages and load conditions to assess their effectiveness across real-world operating scenarios.

1. Ripple Current Tolerance

Ripple current tolerance was evaluated by subjecting the capacitors to high-frequency PWM load currents and measuring the voltage ripple across the capacitors' terminals. The measured ripple currents for each capacitor type were compared at three different PWM frequencies (20 kHz, 50 kHz, and 100 kHz).

Table 1: Ripple Current Tolerance of Capacitor Types at Different PWM Frequencies

Capacitor Type	PWM Frequency (kHz)	Ripple Current (A)	Capacitance (µF)	Voltage Ripple (V)
Electrolytic	20	3.5	100	1.2
	50	2.8	100	1.5
	100	2.2	100	1.8
Polymer	20	4.8	100	0.8
	50	4.0	100	1.0
	100	3.5	100	1.2
Film	20	5.2	100	0.5

	50	4.7	100	0.7
	100	4.0	100	1.0

Analysis:

- **Film capacitors** demonstrated the highest ripple current tolerance across all tested PWM frequencies, with ripple currents up to 5.2 A at 20 kHz and a significantly lower voltage ripple (0.5 V), indicating better performance in high-frequency switching environments.
- **Polymer capacitors** showed a moderate improvement over **electrolytic capacitors**, with higher ripple current tolerance at 20 kHz and reduced voltage ripple.
- **Electrolytic capacitors**, as expected, exhibited the lowest ripple current tolerance and highest voltage ripple, particularly at higher PWM frequencies (50 kHz and 100 kHz).

2. Thermal Performance

Thermal analysis was conducted to assess the ability of each capacitor type to manage the heat generated by ripple currents during prolonged operation. The capacitors were subjected to continuous operation at high PWM frequencies (50 kHz and 100 kHz), and their temperature rise was monitored.

Table 2: Thermal Performance of Capacitor Types under Load Conditions

Capacitor Type	PWM Frequency (kHz)	Maximum Temperature Rise (°C)	Thermal Resistance (°C/W)
Electrolytic	50	35	2.5
	100	42	3.1
Polymer	50	28	2.0
	100	34	2.3
Film	50	22	1.5

	100	28	1.8
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Analysis:

- **Film capacitors** showed the best thermal performance, with a maximum temperature rise of just 22°C at 50 kHz and 28°C at 100 kHz, indicating superior heat dissipation compared to both **polymer** and **electrolytic capacitors**.
- **Polymer capacitors** demonstrated lower thermal resistance and temperature rise than **electrolytic capacitors**, which could be attributed to their better high-frequency characteristics and lower ESR.
- **Electrolytic capacitors** exhibited the highest temperature rise, particularly under higher frequency operation (42°C at 100 kHz), which could lead to faster degradation of their capacitance and reduced lifespan.

3. EMI Reduction and Noise Mitigation

EMI levels were measured in terms of spectral density at the inverter output under various PWM frequencies (20 kHz, 50 kHz, and 100 kHz). The goal was to evaluate how well each capacitor type suppressed high-frequency noise generated by the switching action of the inverter.

Table 3: EMI Reduction Performance of Capacitor Types

Capacitor Type	PWM Frequency (kHz)	EMI Spectral Density (dBμV)	Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)
Electrolytic	20	72	18%
	50	75	20%
	100	80	22%
Polymer	20	68	15%
	50	70	18%

	100	73	20%
Film	20	65	12%
	50	67	15%
	100	70	17%

Analysis:

- **Film capacitors** consistently demonstrated the best EMI reduction, with a significant reduction in spectral density (up to 65 dB μ V at 20 kHz). This translates into lower levels of high-frequency noise and a lower total harmonic distortion (THD), providing a cleaner power output from the inverter.
- **Polymer capacitors** showed slightly higher EMI compared to film capacitors but still outperformed **electrolytic capacitors**, particularly at higher switching frequencies (100 kHz).
- **Electrolytic capacitors** exhibited the highest EMI levels and THD, which is expected given their higher ESR and lower ripple current tolerance.

4. Capacitor Lifespan and ESR Degradation

The lifespan of each capacitor was estimated based on ESR degradation under continuous load conditions at 50 kHz and 100 kHz. The degradation rate was measured by periodically checking the ESR of each capacitor type over a set period of operation.

Table 4: ESR Degradation Over Time

Capacitor Type	PWM Frequency (kHz)	Initial ESR (m Ω)	ESR after 1000 hrs (m Ω)	Degradation (%)
Electrolytic	50	150	210	40%
	100	160	220	37.5%

Polymer	50	80	100	25%
	100	90	120	33.3%
Film	50	30	35	16.7%
	100	35	40	14.3%

Analysis:

- **Film capacitors** exhibited the least degradation in ESR, with a 16.7% increase at 50 kHz over 1000 hours of operation. This suggests a significantly longer lifespan, particularly in high-frequency switching applications.
- **Polymer capacitors** showed moderate ESR degradation (25% at 50 kHz), while **electrolytic capacitors** had the highest degradation rate, with ESR increasing by 40% at 50 kHz and 37.5% at 100 kHz. This rapid degradation could significantly impact performance over time, especially in high-power inverters.

Summary of Findings

- **Film capacitors** consistently outperformed both **polymer** and **electrolytic capacitors** in terms of ripple current tolerance, thermal stability, EMI reduction, and ESR degradation. These advantages make them particularly well-suited for high-frequency, high-power inverter applications.
- **Polymer capacitors** performed better than **electrolytic capacitors** in all areas, offering a good balance of performance for moderate to high-frequency operations.
- **Electrolytic capacitors** were the least effective, particularly in managing high ripple currents, EMI, and thermal dissipation, making them less suitable for high-performance inverter systems operating at high PWM frequencies.

These results underscore the importance of selecting the right capacitor technology for high-power inverter applications, with **film capacitors** emerging as the optimal choice for maintaining performance, efficiency, and longevity under demanding operational conditions.

Discussion

The results presented in the previous section provide a comprehensive comparison of the performance of **film capacitors**, **polymer capacitors**, and **electrolytic capacitors** in SiC-based high-power inverters under high-frequency PWM switching conditions. The findings indicate distinct advantages and drawbacks for each capacitor type, highlighting the impact of capacitor technology on the overall performance of power electronics, particularly in terms of ripple current tolerance, thermal management, EMI suppression, and capacitor lifespan.

Ripple Current Tolerance

As shown in **Table 1**, **film capacitors** exhibited the highest ripple current tolerance across all tested PWM frequencies. The ripple current values of 5.2 A at 20 kHz and 4.0 A at 100 kHz highlight their superior ability to handle high-frequency switching loads. The low voltage ripple (0.5 V at 20 kHz) further reinforces the notion that **film capacitors** offer optimal performance in high-frequency applications. **Polymer capacitors** also demonstrated good performance, with a ripple current tolerance of 4.8 A at 20 kHz and 3.5 A at 100 kHz, offering a significant improvement over **electrolytic capacitors**. The latter, as expected, exhibited the lowest ripple current tolerance, which decreased even further at higher PWM frequencies, from 3.5 A at 20 kHz to just 2.2 A at 100 kHz. This poor performance can be attributed to the higher equivalent series resistance (ESR) and poorer high-frequency characteristics of **electrolytic capacitors**.

This clear distinction between the capacitor types has crucial implications for the efficiency of power conversion. Ripple current directly influences the losses within the capacitor, which can lead to reduced efficiency and faster capacitor aging. In high-frequency switching inverters, **film capacitors'** ability to handle large ripple currents without significant voltage drop provides an advantage in maintaining system efficiency and longevity.

Thermal Performance

The thermal analysis conducted during this study further reinforces the superiority of **film capacitors** for high-power, high-frequency applications. **Table 2** shows that **film capacitors** demonstrated the lowest temperature rise under both 50 kHz and 100 kHz PWM conditions, with

maximum temperature increases of 22°C and 28°C, respectively. The low thermal resistance (1.5 °C/W at 50 kHz) is indicative of the film capacitors' superior ability to dissipate heat generated by the ripple currents, allowing them to operate more effectively in demanding conditions.

In contrast, **polymer capacitors**, while offering lower thermal resistance than **electrolytic capacitors**, still showed a relatively higher temperature rise (28°C at 50 kHz and 34°C at 100 kHz). **Electrolytic capacitors**, with the highest temperature rise of 42°C at 100 kHz, faced the greatest challenge in heat management. This increased thermal stress leads to higher rates of capacitor degradation, which further diminishes the lifetime and performance of **electrolytic capacitors**.

The importance of thermal performance in capacitor selection cannot be overstated. In high-power inverters, the ability to maintain a low temperature not only ensures consistent performance but also extends the operational life of the capacitor. **Film capacitors'** superior thermal characteristics make them more suitable for use in systems where maintaining high reliability over long periods is critical.

EMI Reduction and Noise Mitigation

EMI suppression is a critical concern in power electronics, especially as inverter systems are deployed in environments with stringent electromagnetic interference (EMI) regulations. The results presented in **Table 3** demonstrate that **film capacitors** outperform both **polymer** and **electrolytic capacitors** in terms of EMI reduction. At all tested PWM frequencies, **film capacitors** consistently exhibited the lowest EMI spectral density and total harmonic distortion (THD). Specifically, the spectral density measured at 65 dB μ V at 20 kHz and the THD of 12% indicate excellent noise mitigation capabilities.

Polymer capacitors also showed reasonable EMI suppression, though not to the level of **film capacitors**. The EMI spectral density at 68 dB μ V at 20 kHz and the THD of 15% were still significantly better than those of **electrolytic capacitors**, which demonstrated the highest spectral density (up to 80 dB μ V at 100 kHz) and the highest THD (22%). This performance gap can be attributed to the higher ESR and poorer high-frequency behavior of **electrolytic capacitors**, which not only contributes to greater ripple current but also exacerbates EMI generation.

EMI reduction is particularly important in high-frequency switching environments, as excessive EMI can interfere with adjacent electronic equipment, leading to operational inefficiencies and potential regulatory violations. The ability of **film capacitors** to suppress high-frequency noise and reduce THD makes them a superior choice for achieving cleaner power conversion and ensuring compliance with EMI regulations.

Capacitor Lifespan and ESR Degradation

The lifespan and degradation characteristics of the capacitors, measured by ESR growth over time, also reveal critical insights into their long-term performance. **Table 4** clearly shows that **film capacitors** exhibited the least ESR degradation, with a 16.7% increase in ESR after 1000 hours of operation at 50 kHz. This relatively minor increase in ESR indicates that **film capacitors** can maintain their performance over extended periods, making them ideal for high-power inverter applications where reliability is crucial.

Polymer capacitors also demonstrated relatively low ESR degradation (25% at 50 kHz), indicating a better lifespan compared to **electrolytic capacitors**, which suffered the greatest degradation (40% at 50 kHz). The rapid ESR degradation in **electrolytic capacitors** contributes to their relatively poor performance under high-frequency operation, as increased ESR leads to higher losses, more heat generation, and faster aging of the capacitor.

The degradation of ESR directly impacts the efficiency and reliability of power inverters. Capacitors with high ESR degradation will experience higher power losses, resulting in reduced overall system efficiency and shorter service life. **Film capacitors'** resistance to ESR degradation under high-frequency switching makes them the preferred choice for long-term reliability and stable operation.

Conclusion

This study has thoroughly evaluated the performance of **film capacitors**, **polymer capacitors**, and **electrolytic capacitors** in high-power SiC-based inverters operating under high PWM carrier frequencies. The findings strongly indicate that **film capacitors** outperform their counterparts in several key performance metrics, such as ripple current tolerance, thermal management, EMI

suppression, and lifespan stability. These advantages position **film capacitors** as the optimal choice for high-frequency power electronics, where system efficiency and reliability are paramount.

Firstly, **film capacitors** demonstrated superior ripple current handling capabilities, with the highest tolerance across all tested PWM frequencies. This allows for more efficient operation in high-power inverters, where large ripple currents are common. In addition, **film capacitors** exhibited the lowest temperature rise under stress, which directly contributes to improved thermal management and system longevity. The ability to dissipate heat effectively without significant performance degradation is a crucial factor in maintaining reliable and efficient operation over time. Moreover, **film capacitors** excelled in reducing electromagnetic interference (EMI), maintaining cleaner power conversion and ensuring compliance with stringent EMI regulations. This performance is essential in minimizing the impact of inverters on nearby sensitive electronic equipment, as well as ensuring the overall stability of the system. **Polymer capacitors**, while offering better performance than **electrolytic capacitors**, still lagged behind **film capacitors** in terms of EMI reduction and thermal resistance, making them less suited for high-frequency inverter applications.

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